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Ramil Guliyev
PhD (Art Study)
Institute of Architecture and Art of ANAS
(Azerbaijan)

ramil_amea@mail.ru

SYMBOLIC EMBODIMENT OF THE IMAGE OF HEYDAR ALIYEV IN FINE ART

Abstract. In the works analyzed in the presented article, the embodiment of the image of the national leader of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev by means of symbols is discussed. Addressing this topic, Azerbaijani artists tried to compare the great leader to a tree, a mountain (Ilandag or Hachadag), and the sun, and to make them one with those beings.

The meaning of the compositions, the form of expression differ, and the idea is based on universal principles. Because these symbols have been considered as the main source of belief of the ancient Turks throughout history. Surrounded by these symbols, the image of Heydar Aliyev is remembered as a wise leader and head of state

Key words: Heydar Aliyev, symbol, artist, mountain, sun.

Introduction. This year, May 10 marks the 100th anniversary of the birth of HeydarAliyev, the founder and architect of modern Azerbaijan, who has a special place in the history of our statehood. On the eve of this historic day, the glorious and unique life path of our national leader Heydar Aliyev is once again alive before our eyes with all its splendor.

It is known that the wise head of state spent all his life, struggle, in a word, selfless activity for the development of the political, economic and cultural life of Azerbaijan, and did everything he could to make our republic widely recognized in the international world.

For this reason, the artistic image of the great historical figure Heydar Aliyev is one of the topics of our modern visual art, which is rich in

interesting, relevant and colorful works. Many artists of Azerbaijan and some of the world have created perfect portraits of the great leader from an artistic and aesthetic point of view. All this is a manifestation of love for an eternal, genius personality, devotion from the heart, universal love.

The interpretation of the main material. Artists expressing their love for the National Leader in various forms express their respect and reverence to the memory of the Great Leader by adopting the ideology of Heydar Aliyev and the path defined by him in the portrait genre.

But this expression manifests itself in different forms. Portraits of Heydar Aliyev can be divided into the following types in terms of idea – aesthetic essence and content:

- national-patriotic and state portraits;
- universal (multifaceted) character portraits;
- large portraits;
- lyrical-romantic portraits;
- neutral portraits [3, p. 43].

In the presented works, the meaning load and form of expression of Heydar Aliyev's image are differentiated by means of symbols, and his idea is based on universal principles.

Habiba Allahverdiyeva, born in 1981 in Shahbuz district, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, is an honored artist with special observation ability. The work of Habiba Allahverdiyeva, a member of the Union of Artists, Honored artist of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, stands out for its unique style and originality in the development of our national art school.

His works dedicated to the leaders of the Turkic world, M.K. Atatürk and Heydar Aliyev, “National leaders of the Turkic world” and “Unquenchable Sun of the Azerbaijani People” attract attention with their skillfully executed, full color shades [2, p. 20].

In the work of the talented artist called “National leaders of the Turkic world”, we see the image of Heydar Aliyev and Mustafa Kemal Atatürk on the right and left of the tree whose roots penetrate deep into the earth. In the words of the artist - “The tree symbolizes Turkishness. Turk's strength, power, unity, deep and ancient roots. The branches of the tree represent separate Turkish states...”. With this, the artist tried to bring to the audience's attention that his images are based on All-Turkish roots.

Fig. 1. Habiba Allahverdiyeva. “National leaders of the Turkic world”, oilpaint, canvas, 2011

Habiba Allahverdiyeva’s painting “The Unquenchable Sun of the Azerbaijani People” instills a deep idea and combines the face of the great leader and ancient Turkish symbols – the sun and the mountain – in the majority of the composition. This painting, which impresses the audience, attracts attention with its rich, contrasting color solution and expressive views of the image.

It should also be noted that the sun symbol is widespread among many Turkic peoples and symbolizes life and light. Along with this, we also see the image of the mountain, which a number of artists used when creating the portrait of the Great Leader.

For information, let's note that the Turkish people's belief in the mountains as great, or the name of the mountain as father – Ada-golan, has spread to “Dade Gorgud's book” with various variants. Mythical elements related to the Oghuz getting power from the mountain and its spirit are prominent in the saga [1, p. 49].

One of the commendable works on the subject was created by the talented young artist Tahmina Ali.

Since 2017, he has participated in a number of local and international exhibitions, starting his artistic activity in Ankara, Turkey.

In 2019, he participated in the art exhibition “Peak of Development” with his work “Victory Celebration”. Before long, this painting, which consists of the artist's thoughts, becomes a reality. The artist remembers those moments like this: “With this painting, I wanted to revive our heroic Army behind our President, our national leader Heydar Aliyev, who laid the foundations of the road to our glorious Victory, and our brave men who died for Karabakh. At the same time, the work glorifies the freedom of Karabakh and Shusha. I tried to express the joy of Victory in my heart with this work”.

In addition, in the background of the compositions of Ramil Ahmadov and Javid Ismayilov, we find a majestic mountain image. As we all know, this mountain is Hachadag, Ilandag, located in Julfa district of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

We would like to express the meaning-content burden that this mountain carries with the words of Nikas Safronov, a famous Russian artist and a full member of the Russian Academy of Arts, during his meeting with the Supreme Leader: “You see, in the center of the painting, Ilandag rises majestically, illuminated by the sun's rays filtering through the clouds. Archaeological excavations are being carried out at the foot of the mountain. By describing this scene, I wanted to confirm the antiquity of the land of Nakhchivan, which gave birth to great people like you and has a special inner energy...” [3, p. 122].

The variety of ideas and content of the image of Heydar Aliyev in fine art allows artists to give space to the synthesis of style and details. In some works,

the internal unity and communication of symbols with different meanings comes to the fore. The author of the presented work is Intigam Jafarov, born in 1986, a member of the Union of Artists. In 2013, the artist, who prefers the genre of portraits and landscapes, created the compositions “Messenger of Peace” and “Toward the Light” in 2013

Fig. 2. Intigam Jafarov. “Messenger of Peace”, oilpainting. canvas, 2013.

The artist’s opinions about both works indicate that the painting has a rich meaning and has a unique symbolic character: the image of two great state leaders was created in the work called “Messenger of Peace”. Holding the flags of Azerbaijan and Turkey in her hands, the image of a mother looking at the sunshine and the future with hope. The arms surrounding it, holding each other, are the soldiers standing guard of our homeland. The combination of flags is a symbol of friendship and brotherhood. The raised hand in front is a sign of the monument that was once placed on the border of Turkey. It actually belongs to us, as a symbol of Turkish-Azerbaijani friendship, it was

given as a sign of help, and the baby on it is in safe hands. In the other work “Toward the Light”, HeydarAliyev means a policy that leads us to the future, to the light, a path, a policy that leads to peace. I have tried to show that the future of people of any age is towards the light...”.

Fig. 3. Sevinj Karimova. “Heydar Aliyev”, oilpaint, canvas, 2020.

On the occasion of the 97th anniversary of the birth of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, Sevinj Karimova, the fine arts teacher of secondary school No. 257, who won the online drawing competition “Savior of Azerbaijan” held by the Yasamal district HeydarAliyev Center, was awarded a diploma and a gift for her work. The talented artist speaks in the language of colors in his work - “Since all the good deeds done by the great leader in his time served the development of our art and the recognition and promotion of Azerbaijan as a whole, he will be remembered from time to time and will never be forgotten.

In this sense, the marks he left on our national cultural history are indelible and eternal...”. The figure eight, as a symbol of eternity, in the light of time, reflects the selfless work of the National leader in the field of culture and art, and the achievements obtained as a result of this work and passed on to future generations [4].

Conclusion. The great leader’s multifaceted goal-oriented activity and well-thought-out policy played an important role in the formation of the basic principles of modern Azerbaijani statehood. Therefore, it can be boldly said that the artistic image of the wise head of state serves national values even if it is created in a symbolic sense. The image of Heydar Aliyev surrounded by figurative and associative symbols in these works distinguished by their originality, perfection of artistic form and innovation is remembered as a wise leader and head of state.

REFERENCES:

1. Əlibəyli R. Dədə Qorqud Kitabı”nda Dağ Kultu.// Dədə Qorqud. Elmi-ədəbi toplusu, III (12). – Bakı, 2004.
2. Hümətov Ə. Uğurlar təsadüfi deyil. – Bakı, 2017.
3. Salamzadə Ə.Ə., Zeynalov X.A. Təsviri sənətdə Heydər Əliyev obrazı. – Bakı, 2019.
4. <https://bakimektebleri.edu.az/257/az/news/read/111568>

Ramil Quliyev (Azərbaycan)

TƏSVİRİ SƏNƏTDƏ HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV OBRAZININ SİMVOLİK TƏCƏSSÜMÜ

Təqdim olunan məqalədə təhlil olunan əsərlərdə Azərbaycanın ümummillili lideri Heydər Əliyevin obrazının simvollar vasitəsi ilə təcəssümündən söz açılmışdır. Bu mövzuya müraciət edən Azərbaycan rəssamları Ulu Öndəri ağaca, dağa (İlandağ və ya Hacadağ), günəşə bənzətməyə, həmin varlıqlarla bir vəhdətdə verməyə çalışıblar.

Kompozisiyaların məna yükü, ifadə forması fərqlənərək, ideyası ümumbəşəri prinsiplərə əsaslanır. Çünki bu simvollar tarix boyu qədim türklərin əsas inanc mənbəyi olan simvoldan sayılıblar. Bu simvollarla simvollarla əhatələnən Heydər Əliyev obrazı müdrik lider, dövlət rəhbəri kimi yadda qalır

Açar sözlər: Heydər Əliyev, simvol, rəssam, dağ, günəş.

Рамиль Гулиев (Азербайджан)

СИМВОЛИЧЕСКОЕ ВОПЛОЩЕНИЕ ОБРАЗА ГЕЙДАРА АЛИЕВА В ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОМ ИСКУССТВЕ

В произведениях, проанализированных в представленной статье, упоминается воплощение образа общенационального лидера Азербайджана Гейдара Алиева посредством символов. Обращаясь к этой теме, азербайджанские художники пытались сравнить великого вождя с деревом, горой (Иландаг или Хаджадаг) и солнцем и сделать их едиными с этими существами.

Смысл композиций, форма выражения различаются, а идея строится на универсальных принципах. Потому что эти символы считались основным источником веры древних тюрков на протяжении всей истории. В окружении этих символов образ Гейдара Алиева запоминается как мудрый лидер и глава государства.

Ключевые слова: ГейдарАлиев, символ, художник, горы, солнце.